

Evergreen

Generation-

Foreign origin.First launched in 2006.

Language - Perl,PostgreSQL,JavaScript,Mozilla's XUL(XML+ JavaScript),Python.

Availability-

It is an open access software.

Accessibility-

It is an open source software.

Strength-

This software is robust,secure,flexible and stable.

Nature of libraries-

Large library system.

System architecture-

It is primarily written in Perl and PostgreSQL with a few sections rewritten in C.The catalogue interface is constructed using Temple Toolkit. The staff client user interface is rewritten in Mozilla's XUL. Python is used for the internationalization build infrastructure.New interface work is being done in Angular.

Database-

It runs on linux servers and uses PostgreSQL for its backend database.

User-friendliness-

It is a user -friendly software.

Limitations-

It requires technical expertise. It has longer implementation cycles.

Opinion- Evergreen is a fairly matured software.

Sources-

Koha

Generation

Koha is the first open source ILS. It was released in 2000 as open source.

Language

Perl,MySQL,Apache

Availability

Koha is an open access software.

Accessibility

Koha is an open source software.

Strength

It supports 24×7 mode of access for both staff and users. At the server level we just need to install Koha and the client machine can access the Koha server through a web browser.

Nature of libraries

Large and medium library systems.

System architecture

Koha is based on web architecture.Both staff interface for professional activities and public access interface for retrieval are available through web browser.A web browser like firefox, chrome may act as client software at end user terminal.

Database

Koha uses SQL database as backend and it's cataloguing data stored in MARC and is accessible via Z39.50 protocol.

User friendliness

It is a user-friendly software.

Limitations

The actual challenge is the inability of librarians to use Koha. The other challenges were poor internet connectivity, lack of technical support and difficulties upgrading and backing up the Koha database.

Opinion

Koha is translated in over 100 languages and is implemented in more than 900 institutions around the world.

Source

NewGenLib

Generation

It was started as commercial ILS in 2005 and made available as open source ILS under GNU GPL in 2008.

Language

PostgreSQL, Apache Tomcat and Solr Lucene.

Availability

It is a free and open access software.

Accessibility

It is an open source software.

Strength

It uses several well supported and widely used, reliable and well tested open source components.

Nature of libraries

Medium range library system.

System architecture

It is an entirely Java based platform. Tomcat is used for servers. Hibernate is used for the framework, JDOM for XML messaging etc.

Database

JavaSE, Apache Tomcat, Spring framework, Hibernate, Lucene and Solr, Java servlets, java server pages. It is entirely Java based, platform-neutral, and uses these major software technologies in its presentation, web server and database layers.

User friendliness

It is a user -friendly ILS.

Limitations

Opinion

It is the first open source ILS released from India. It is now a mature open source ILS.

Source

PMB

Generation

The first version was released in 2003 and the latest version is 4.1 released in march 2014.

Language

Availability

It is an open access software.

Accessibility

It is an open source software.

Strength

It is supporting authority file management [software](#). It has the facility to search formulas, links to search external sources, shelf management, basic cataloguing of different document forms, online help etc.

Nature of libraries

Small library system.

System architecture

It is a web enabled ILS and is using XAMP architecture (X-any OS; Apache as web server, PHP as a programming environment, MySQL as RDMS). It is also using AJAX to support interactive and collaborative frameworks.

Database

It is based on web architecture. It means that only the server version is required to be installed and in client machines Web browsers (firefox, chrome, etc.) may act as client software to access the PMB server.

User friendliness

It is a user-friendly software.

Limitations

The problem of this open source ILS is that the PMB portal is available in french language only and this ILS supports only UNIMARC format.

Opinion

This ILS is available in 4 language interfaces (English, French, Spanish, Italian). This platform supports all basic library automation workflow alongside some advanced features like OPAC 2.0 and electronic SDI service.

Source

LIBSYS

Generation

It was developed by Libsys Corporation, New Delhi in 1984.

Language

This ILS is written in Java and C/C++.

Availability

It is a close-access commercial ILS.

Accessibility

It is a close source ILS.

Strength

Smart, streamlined, and scalable, effortless procurement, maximum efficiency.

Nature of libraries

Large library system.

System architecture

It is built around its indigenous bibliographic database following ANSI Z39.2 format.

Database

It is based on its own bibliographic database but with changing time it is also available for the environment using Oracle (or SQL server or MySQL) as back-end RDBMS.

User friendliness

User friendly software.

Limitations

Opinion

It is presently available in six different editions or versions to suit requirements of different types of libraries.

Source

SLIM

Generation

Language

Availability

It is a free and open source software.

Accessibility

The source code is available for any [platform.It](#) is a close source commercial software.

Strength

Nature of libraries

Medium range library system.

System architecture

It is based on the LAMP structure. L- Linux,A-Apache,M-MySQL,P-PhP.

Database

User friendliness

It is a user-friendly software.

Limitations

Opinion It is a complete library management system from Indonesia.

Source

SOUL

Generation

The first version of SOUL was released in February 1999 at Nagpur. SOUL 2.0 was released in January 2009.

Language

It uses RDBMS MSSQL to organize data.

Availability

It is a close source commercial ILS.

Accessibility

Strength

Nature of libraries

Medium range library system.

System architecture

It is a client-server architecture based system.

Database

SOUL 2.0 provides two options for backend DBMS- MS-SQL and MySQL.

User friendliness

It is a window based user friendly system.

Limitations

Opinion

Source